

1. Introduction

Tree planting for Natural Flood Management (NFM) is prominent in UK policy strategy and guidance, despite a lack of empirical evidence (Lane, 2017). Furthermore its implementation is recognised as a ‘wicked’ environmental challenge (Dadson et al., 2017) where solutions are complex and require new approaches (Functowicz & Ravetz, 1993). Yet Natural Flood Management approaches have remained traditional technocratic (Wingfield et al., 2021) despite work demonstrating the neglect of lay or place-based expertise and the impact this has on science and policy has a well-evidenced literature (e.g. Wynne, 2016).

In responding to tackling these challenges this research used Participatory GIS as a key tool in understanding the importance of place-based knowledge and how this may impact and inform the prospect of increasing tree cover for NFM.

2. Methods

Participatory mapping and GIS (PGIS) are well established (Pánek, 2016) with a range of methodologies being used to tackle subjects in both physical and social geographic disciplines, with examples of boundary work across both disciplines and knowledges (e.g. Baldauf McBride et al, 2017)

Working in a case study rural river catchment of +100km² this research used a mixed methods approach combining long, semi-structured interviews with participatory mapping on scale maps of field boundaries, that were re-digitised in ArcGIS Pro to provide a GIS dataset. Participants were identified from over 22 sites, across a wide range of rural land holdings ranging from 5 to 1000acres. During interviews participants were encouraged to annotate maps, a method which served multiple purposes including recording place location of physical features, routes, future or past tree cover plans, locations of experiences etc.

The participant maps were then combined with physical and remote sensed data as well as being region coded alongside the interviews in Nvivo. The coded maps and interviews formed a combined dataset which was used to explore impacts including that of place-based expertise.

Figure 1: A participant map identified a field suitable for tree planting – polygons drawn over the re-digitised and geo-located map were used to identify spatial features of the proposed woodland including total area, slope, current soil type etc. The same region coded in NVivo directly relates the annotations to the interview extract in which the participant discusses their family preferences for this woodland.

To understand the potential impact of increased tree cover on catchment hydrology a heuristic hydrological model that could evaluate the impacts of alternative land use scenarios was developed for the catchment using SHETRAN (Ewen, Parkin and O’Connell, 2000). Physical features and preferences identified in the mapping dataset were used to inform and develop a model of the catchment for a time period that included significant flood events and alternative land-use scenarios directly informed by the participant maps were modelled to explore changes to the catchment hydrology.

3. Research Themes relating to PGIS

3.1. PGIS can record lived experience and place-based expertise that is of direct importance to scientific practice and knowledge

The information from the mapping activity was able to capture and directly inform the physical dataset necessary for the accurate development of a hydrological model. For example, participants place-based expertise identified important factors in stormflow which would not be apparent from instrumented data, for example over ground sheet flow and base flow / increased saturation, knowledge of which directly informed model choice and baseline validation.

Locations and quality of hydrological features such as land drains were identified, as well as areas where this knowledge had been lost and would generate uncertainty in model output. This evidence supported model development and also informed the constraints and uncertainties of the model.

Physical features described by participants could be accurately mapped by relating them to the

physical data-sets and analysed for the development of alternative scenarios. For example, participant information on maps enabled the researcher to identify slopes they perceived as ‘too steep’, a complex factor significantly dependent on the socio-cultural implications of machinery and risk, as well as physical factors of slippage and soil type, and therefore suitable for tree cover. Alternative scenarios for the model were developed that examined the hydrological impacts of tree cover on these alternative cover scenarios, which reflected farm preferences and related to the wider landscape context. Place-based expertise directly informed the development of these scenarios and enabled them to reflect real-world options and preferences.

3.2. Lived experience and place-based expertise highlighted the blurred boundaries between social and physical geographical data and the challenges this creates

Technocratic approaches tend, by nature and institutional structure to be disciplinary, and whilst science is working hard to stretch outside this, scientific knowledge struggles to cross these boundaries (Tett, 2015). Place-based expertise is less confined by these disciplinary structures suggesting further its importance in tackling wicked challenges. When participants described features or information within the landscape their place-based knowledge was not restricted by discipline but recognised the landscape as both socio-cultural and physical. Landscapes were understood within narrative context, that directly related physical features to socio-cultural factors and visa versa. For example, water flow may have changed direction due to the historical management, draining or dredging in a manner which affected flow, or due physical impacts of vegetation, loose soils, rockfall, which in turn may have been affected by management choices, or weather, climate, or a lorry cracking a bridge. Trying to separate out these behaviours to ‘discipline’ the dataset is potentially impossible and creates scenarios which bear no resemblance to the entwined real world systems.

Working with these entangled real-world systems leads to discipline-based challenges based on methodological practice. The well-evidenced ethical practices of social sciences often rely on maintaining confidentiality for participants, whereas a physical dataset can be collected without an ethical process taking place. This practice of PGIS has demonstrated that a physical dataset can be seen to be inherently socio-cultural. Removing location data restricts the further usefulness of this dataset or the ability of others to validate output using normal methods. However, sharing the full dataset would potentially enable the identification of participants, thus removing their confidentiality. This has considerable ethical implications which will need resolving and raises much broader methodological questions for both disciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches.

4. Conclusion

Participatory GIS has been demonstrated to be a useful methodological tool for collecting and working with interdisciplinary datasets. It enables the triangulation of different types of data that inform us about landscapes.

This case study demonstrates the importance of place-based expertise and mapping captured key factors that can inform scientific practice and policy making when tackling problems such as tree planting for Natural Flood Management.

However, ethical challenges including maintaining confidentiality, value of and ownership of data arise, and further work is needed to address this as different challenges will require different and well-argued methodological approaches. This should not be considered purely an interdisciplinary problem but a disciplinary one, as this work supports wider literatures demonstrating the socio-cultural importance of physical datasets; this needs careful consideration and further discussion.

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Biographies

Jenny is a Leverhulme Trust Doctoral Scholar as part of the Forest Edge programme at BIFoR, University of Birmingham. She backgrounds in both social and physical sciences and has relished this interdisciplinary challenge. She is entangled in landscapes and would spend her time walking her dogs if she wasn’t working.